

CHARACTERIZATION OF NANOFIBROUS SCAFFOLD FROM BLENDS OF GELATIN/PCL/CMC BY USING ELECTROSPINNING TECHNIQUE

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Abstract

Improvement of gelatin fibrous scaffold by electrospinning technique allows the preparation of ultrafine fibers with diameters ranging from micron to nanoscale fibrous materials. The electrospinning is a novel and efficient fabrication process that produced electrospun fibers through the action of an external electric field to create an electrically charged jet of polymer solution and it can able to be used as a wound closure material or tissue caused by an accident or by diseases etc. Include the development of characteristic to optimize for all applications and reduce the cost of the raw materials and develop to be used in a variety of applications. This research selected gelatin blended with polycaprolactone cellulose and carboxymethyl fabricated by using electrospinning technique for nanofibrous scaffold. We used design of experiment with voltage and feed rate for the ratios of gelatin/polycaprolactone were 100/0/0, 90/5/5, 80/15/5, 70/25/5 and 60/35/5, respectively. Gelatin and mixture was used to produce nanofiber scaffold in order to analyze fiber's physical characteristic. The gelatin solution made from dissolving gelatin in water which serves as solvent for the solution because water is a great solvent for gelatin. However, the solution used in fiber production with electrospinning, this research used organic solvent, 2,2,2-trifluoroethanol, which is also a good solvent for gelatin PCL and CMC was dissolved in water instead hence produces good raw material for fiber production using electrospinning. To characterize the scaffolds, we analyzed the physical properties by investigating the morphology and measuring the fibers size using Scanning Electron Microscope revealed that when PCL increased from 0 to 35 percent CMC set at 0 to 5 percent, fiber's size was decreased from 1.2 nm to 7.1 nm. Swelling ratio mixture of G100 ratio had swelling ratio of 11.74%. When adding more PCL, there will be more fiber as well, so the % can be remembered.

Keywords: Scaffold, Gelatin, Poly Caprolactone, Carboxymethylcellulose, Electrospinning.

1. INTRODUCTION

Electrospinning is a fiber production method that can produce extremely small, in the order of nanometer, fiber from synthetic polymer or natural polymer. Electrospinning uses the principle of difference in potential [1] to deliver polymer to the collector. The size of the fiber is depended on the voltage, material's flow rate, distance between the injector and the collector for fiber and concentration of the material. The result of electrospun fiber can be in the form of non-woven fiber and aligned fiber. Electrospinning is popular among various industries, including in medicine such as for production of prosthetic skin and

wound dressing material [2]. At present, researchers and doctors are thinking of ways to produce artificial skin or synthetic skin, and cell scaffolds [3]. Biodegradable Come to transplant the wound area. By using various types of natural polymers that are cheap and easily available, such as gelatin, collagen and chitosan [4]. In forming the structure this is for convenience and speed. And in case of wounds on the skin that have a wide area making it impossible to find other parts of skin to replace The important function of such skin substitutes is to stimulate the main cells in the dermis layer, namely fibroblast cells [5]. Around the wound growth and mobile come into structure and change shape into complete tissue [6]. Fibroblasts are the main cells in the production of collagen, which serve as the structure of the skin and keep it healthy. And create elastin [7]. To help make the skin flexible [8]. Collagen is used as a natural cell scaffold in commercially available forms. Depending on the usefulness of the application [9]. The structural strength and biodegradability depend on the bonding linkage.

Gelatin is a type of protein produced by the breakdown of collagen by acids or alkalis. It looks like a light brown powder. It can be extracted from bones and skins of animals (such as cattle, buffalo, pigs). When gelatin powder is heated with water at about 32 degrees Celsius, it melts into a viscous liquid. Set aside to cool. The liquid sets to form a gel (a jelly-like appearance). Gelatin is used as a component of many products such as cosmetics, drugs, food, and photographic film [1]. In pharmaceuticals, gelatin is used. It is used in tablet coating, hard capsules and soft capsules for pharmaceutical packaging [10]. In agriculture, it is used as an intermediate for minerals needed to grow plants, etc. [11]. In food products, it has many uses.

Polycaprolactone classified as a type of thermoplastic Classified as a polyester with a straight chain. Can be biodegradable. Currently, polycaprolactone. Much attention has been paid to the development of biodegradable plastics. But biodegradable plastics containing 45% starch mixed with polycaprolactone. still not strong enough for use Because it has a melting point of only 60 degrees Celsius and begins to soften at 40 degrees Celsius, which is a limitation in use. Use of polycaprolactone It is commonly used as an additive to resins to improve process ability and improve other properties such as impact properties. Flexibility due to polycaprolactone it can be easily combined with other materials. Therefore, the use of gelatin mixed with polycaprolactone is used to produce artificial or synthetic skin [12]. or cell cultures biodegradable

However, because gelatin is quite expensive; in order to reduce the cost of prosthetic skin, it is necessary to mix gelatin with other cheaper natural polymer. Therefore, carboxymethyl cellulose or CMC is an interesting candidate in this research. It can improve the strength of prosthetic skin as well. This is because CMC is being used widely in many industries such as in industrial production of detergent, paint, glue, fabric, paper, ceramic, food and medicine. Moreover, CMC is colorless, odorless, does not present any harmful effect to human and a very efficient water soluble substance [13]. CMC or cellulose derivative is generally made of cellulose tissue that has high amount of alpha cellulose which is generally known as high quality cellulose and it is also cheaper than gelatin. Moreover, in order to increase the fiber's mechanical strength, this research applied the crosslinking technique by using high temperature or dehydrothermal

treatment (DHT). DHT is a physical process which concerns giving high thermal energy under vacuum to the material. Normally, this process used over 100°C which extracted water from the fiber and cause condensation process that could produce the crosslinking of material and strengthens the fiber [12]. Gelatin is a type of natural biopolymer and can be extracted from collagen which is a substance that can be found abundantly in animal's skin, meat and bone. Gelatin also has another special characteristic such as highly biodegradable material and even though gelatin is hydrophilic polymer. It cannot be mixed and formed into fiber by electrospinning. Therefore, this research used a solvent that could efficiently dissolve gelatin, 2, 2, 2 trifluoroethanol with the weight/volume percentage concentration of 10wt % [14]. Research Objective Study and develop skin cell scaffolds by mixing gelatin-containing scaffolds of polycaprolactone and carboxymethyl cellulose with electrospinning technique.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Gelatin/PCL/CMC scaffold preparation

Gelatin from Porcine Skin, 180 G Bloom, in powder form, Type B, from Fluka Analytical and 2, 2, 2-trifluoroethanol (TFE) (purity 99.0%) from Sigma-Aldrich were prepared. Preparation of gelatin solution was made by dissolving gelatin in TFE and stirred the solution at temperature of 60 C°, 300 rpm. For 30 minute at the concentration of 10 %.

Poly (ε-caprolactone) (PCL), with an average molecular weight of 80,000 (80kDa) is bioresorbable and biocompatible, and has been studied as a wound dressing material since in the 1970s. Extensive research had been conducted on its biocompatibility and efficacy, both in vitro and in vivo, resulting in FDA approval of a number of medical and drug delivery devices that are composed of PCL. At present, PCL is being regarded as a soft- and hard-tissue-compatible bioresorbable material poly (ε-caprolactone) of with 2, 2, 2-trifluoroethanol (TFE) as the solvent. Preparation of PCL solution was made by dissolving PCL in TFE and stirred the solution at temperature of 60 C°, 300 rpm. For 30 minutes at the concentration of 15 %.

Carboxymethylcellulose sodium salt (CMC) was purchased from Sigma-Aldrich, St. Louis, MO, USA. It was medium viscosity with 400-800 cps in a 2% aqueous solution at 25 C°. The Carboxymethylcellulose sodium salt (CMC) solution was prepared by mixing powder with DI water at 0.8wt% (w/w) then leaved it at temperature of 60 C°, 300 rpm. For 60 minute. Mix Gelatin with PCL and CMC solution at temperature of 60 C°, 300 rpm. For 30 minute. Analytical were prepared by the ratio of gelatin/PCL/CMC as shown in Table 1.

Table 1: The ratio of Gelatin/PCL/CMC

Gelatin (%)	PCL (%)	CMC (%)	Code
100	0	0	G100
90	5	5	G91
80	15	5	G82
70	25	5	G73
60	35	5	G64

2.2 Electrospinning technique

Gelatin/PCL/CMC solutions were prepared at the ratios of 100/0/0, 90/5/5, 80/15/5, 70/25/5 and 60/35/5 for fiber production by using electrospinning process was schematically shown in Fig. 1.

The mixture was added into 5 ml syringe and the syringe was then attached to needle spinneret #20 with the hole size of 0.9 mm. The flow was controlled using syringe pump (KD-100, KD Scientific, Inc., USA) at the feed rate of 0.5 ml/h. High voltage electricity was supplied from high voltage power supply (RR501.25R/230/DDPM, Gamma High Voltage Research, USA) at 20 kV.

The mixture was then injected on to collector which diameter 100 mm. 120 rpm. Was made of foil sheet. The distance between the needle's end to the foil sheet was 13 centimeters.

Figure 1: Schematic Diagram of Electrospinning Apparatus

2.3 Dehydrothermal Treatment (DHT)

The resulted scaffold was then put into crosslinking technique by using DHT. The scaffold of gelatin PCL and CMC mixtures at the ratio of 100/0/0, 90/5/5, 80/15/5, 70/25/5 and 60/35/5 was put into desiccator with silica gel in vacuum container for 48 hours. Then the scaffold was put into vacuum oven under the temperature of 140°C for 48 hours.

2.4 Swelling ratio

The scaffold was put into the swelling test in order to find the difference of dry weight and wet weight of the scaffold in percentage. The dried scaffold was weighted and then soaked the scaffold under PBS buffer solution at the pH of 7.4 and temperature of 37°C for 3 hours. Then both sides of the scaffold were wiped with low lint paper 10 seconds for each side and then weighted immediately. The dry weight and wet weight were then

calculated into percentage using the following formula as shown in (1). We then compared the resulted of swelling ratio of scaffolds from electrospinning technique.

$$Swelling\ ratio = \frac{W_{so} - W_o}{W_o} \quad (1)$$

Where as

W_{so} is the weight of scaffold after its water content was absorbed

W_o is the initial weight of the scaffold

Figure 2: Flow process chart

3. RESULTS

3.1 Surface morphology of nanofibrous scaffolds

The scaffold was analyzed its morphology by using scanning electron microscopy (SEM, EM30P-AX, COXEM(KR)) at the voltage of 20 kV with magnification power 1000x after it has been coated with gold(Gold (Au), SPT-20, COXEM(KR)) [15]. The fiber's thicknesses were also measured for at least 5 values and then calculated for the average thickness.

Figure 3: SEM images of scaffolds for nanofibers Electrospinning with Gelatin/PCL/CMC ratios of 100/0/0 (A), Gelatin/PCL/CMC ratios of 90/5/5 (B), Gelatin/PCL/CMC ratios of 80/15/5 (C), Gelatin/PCL/CMC ratios of 70/25/5 (D), Gelatin/PCL/CMC ratios of 60/35/5 (E) and all condition were DHT for 48h

Table 2: Fiber Diameters of Electrospinning Gelatin/ PCL/CMC

Gelatin/PCL/CMC	Range of diameter (μm)	Average diameter (μm)
100/0/0	4.4-7.1	6.1
90/5/5	1.5-1.9	1.7
80/15/5	1.2-1.9	1.5
70/25/5	2.5-3.1	2.8
60/35/5	1.9-2.3	2.1

Table 2 revealed that when PCL increased from 0 to 35 percent CMC set at 0 to 5 percent, fiber's size was decreased from 1.2 μm to 7.1 μm . SEM images of scaffolds for nanofibers electrospinning with Gelatin/PCL/CMC ratios of 100/0/0 size of the round fiber is Range of diameter 4.4 μm to 7.1 μm Average diameter 6.1 μm , Gelatin/PCL/CMC ratios of 90/5/5 size of the round fiber is Range of diameter 1.5 μm to 1.9 μm Average diameter 1.7 μm , Gelatin/PCL/CMC ratios of 80/15/5 size of the round fiber is Range of diameter 1.2 μm to 1.9 μm Average diameter 1.5 μm , Gelatin/PCL/CMC ratios of 70/25/5 size of the round fiber is Range of diameter 2.5 μm to 3.1 μm Average diameter 2.8 μm , Gelatin/PCL/CMC ratios of 60/35/5 size of the round fiber is Range of diameter 1.9 μm to 2.3 μm Average diameter 2.1 μm .

Figure 4: Show Graph of the resulting fiber slope from molding

Fig. 4. Gelatin/PCL/CMC ratios of 100/0/0 Average diameter 6.1 μm it has the highest slope. Next Gelatin/PCL/CMC ratios of 70/25/5 Average diameter 2.8 μm, Next Gelatin/PCL/CMC ratios of 60/35/5 Average diameter 2.1 μm, Next Gelatin/PCL/CMC ratios of 90/5/5 Average diameter 1.7 μm and Gelatin/PCL/CMC ratios of 80/15/5 Average diameter 1.5 μm respectively.

Table 3: Swelling ratio of scaffolds from Electrospinning

Code	%				
G100	11.51	12.03	11.62	11.31	12.22
G91	5.11	5.22	5.28	5.98	6.12
G82	4.33	4.41	4.32	4.78	4.36
G73	7.60	7.02	6.98	6.99	7.22
G64	5.44	6.01	6.89	6.54	4.34

Table 3 Swelling ratio of scaffolds from electrospinning were also measured for at 5 values and then calculated for the average. The dry weight and wet weight calculated into percentage using formula as shown in (1) swelling ratio of scaffolds from electrospinning technique.

Figure 5: swelling ratio of scaffolds from electrospinning

Fig. 5 revealed that the scaffolds from electrospinning with the mixture of G100 ratio had swelling ratio of 11.74% which was the highest. All scaffolds from electrospinning had average lower in swelling ratio compared with the scaffolds, except for the case of gelatin PCL and CMC mixture at the ratio of G91 which was 5.54%, G82 which was 4.44%, G73 which was 7.16 % and G64 which was 5.84% [16].

4. CONCLUSION

Gelatin/PCL/CMC fiber produced by electrospinning technique revealed is a novel and efficient fabrication process that produced electrospun fibers through the action of an external electric field to create an electrically charged jet of polymer solution and it can able to be used as a wound closure when PCL increased from 0 to 35 percent CMC set at 0 to 5 percent, the ratios of gelatin /polycaprolactone were 100/0/0, 90/5/5, 80/15/5, 70/25/5 and 60/35/5, respectively.

Gelatin/PCL/CMC fiber produced by electrospinning technique revealed that the highest in swelling ratio and the largest of fiber size was found in gelatin and PCL mixture at the ratio of 100/0. Adding PCL into the gelatin fiber occurred in smaller in fiber size and lower in swelling ratio compared with pure gelatin fibrous scaffold. We could summarize that size of the fiber effected to the swelling ratio which the smaller of fiber, the lower of swelling ratio was found. Analyzing the nanofibrous scaffold produced by using.

Analyzing the nanofibrous scaffold produced by using electrospinning technique, the gelatin/PCL/CMC fiber with large fiber size would also has high swelling ratio. Mixture of G100 ratio had swelling ratio of 11.74%. When adding more PCL and CMC, there will be more fiber as well, so the % can be remembered.

Recommendation

1. Solvent Gelatin PCL and CMC which saves money which will help you earn 50% But it is necessary to find securities to audit before auditing.
2. Residues in the testing laboratory are air purified to the air can be distilled. Before doing any inspections, a plan must be made every time.
3. The test, once obtained, may be expected to pass because it requires multiple controls.

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